

Data for Re-evaluating Probable Maximum Precipitation Estimates: Sensitivity to Transposition Domains and Storm Rotation Using Modern Datasets

This repository provides the processed datasets and final figures supporting the systematic re-evaluation of Probable Maximum Precipitation (PMP) estimates for the Red Rock watershed in Iowa. The study quantifies the sensitivity of PMP to storm selection, transposition domain size, maximization procedures (using ERA5 precipitable water), and storm rotation, using modern AORC rainfall data (2002–2023).

The transposition domain presented here corresponds to the largest geographic extent explored in the analysis, referred to as "Domain 4." This domain is bounded by the northwest coordinates 44.66°N, -99.83°W and the southeast coordinates 34.97°N, -87.87°W, spanning a broad portion of the central U.S. Midwest. Domain 4 defines the spatial region from which candidate extreme storms were identified and evaluated for transposition over the Red Rock watershed.

Repository Structure

- **Codes/**: Jupyter Notebooks used to build the figures from the data tables in **Data/**.
- **Data/**: CSV files containing basin-level rainfall values, storm dates, and maximization factor tables used in the PMP calculations.
- **Figure/**: Output figures produced by the notebooks in **Codes/**.

Codes

- **01_Figure_PMP_all_domains_no_rotation.ipynb**: Generates the figure showing PMP estimates across all domains without storm rotation.
- **02_Figure_PMP_rotation_domain4_CW_15days.ipynb**: Generates the figure for Domain 4 with all storm rotations, using a 15-day maximization window.
- **03_Figure_PMP_rotation_domain4_CW_45days.ipynb**: Generates the figure for Domain 4 with all storm rotations, using a 45-day maximization window.
- **04_Figure_PMP_rotation_domain4_CW_75days.ipynb**: Generates the figure for Domain 4 with all storm rotations, using a 75-day maximization window.

Each notebook reads tables from **Data/** and writes outputs to **Figure/**. Open a notebook, run all cells, and the corresponding figure will be reproduced.

Data

The **Data/** folder contains the tabular inputs used throughout the analysis. File-level intents are listed below; consult each CSV header for exact column names.

- **Basin_Rainfall.csv**: Basin-level rainfall metrics for the reference (non-rotated) storm set across domains.
- **Basin_Rainfall_Rotations.csv**: Basin-level rainfall metrics for rotated storms (Domain 4 rotation experiments).
- **Dates_PMP_Storms.csv**: Calendar dates for PMP candidate storms by domain.

- `Dates_Rotated_Storms_Domain4.csv`: Calendar dates associated with rotated storms in Domain 4.
- `IPMF_Factors.csv` and `IPMF_Factors_{0,1,2}.csv`: Factor tables used in PMP maximization (base and domain/period partitions).
- `IPMF_Factors_Domain4_Rotations_{0,1,2}.csv`: Factor tables specific to Domain 4 rotation experiments.
- `MTF_Factors.csv` and `MTF_Factors_{0,1,2}.csv`: Additional maximization factor tables (base and domain/period partitions).
- `MTF_Factors_Domain4_Rotations_{0,1,2}.csv`: Domain 4 rotation variants of MTF factor tables.
- `Maximization_Factors.csv` and `Maximization_Factors_{0,1,2}.csv`: Aggregated/combined factors used to compute PMP.
- `Maximization_Factors_Domain4_Rotations_{0,1,2}.csv`: Combined factors for Domain 4 rotation scenarios.
- `Maximized_PMP_Values.csv`: Final PMP values produced after applying the maximization factors.
- `storm_total_precip.csv`: Total precipitation per storm ID. See the important Storm ID note below.

Shapefiles

- `NHDI_watershed.shp`: Shapefile for the Red Rock watershed used in spatial analyses and figure generation.
- `SST_domain_4.shp`: Shapefile for the transposition domain (Domain 4) used in the analysis.

Important — Storm ID Indexing

- `storm_total_precip.csv` uses the storm index that directly matches the Storm ID presented in the paper.
- All other CSV files in `Data/` use a reversed (flipped) storm numbering relative to the papers. For a 10-storm set, the mapping is: 1 ↔ 10, 2 ↔ 9, 3 ↔ 8, 4 ↔ 7, 5 ↔ 6. In other words, "Storm 1" in those CSVs corresponds to "Storm 10" in the paper, and vice versa.

Please keep this indexing detail in mind when cross-referencing tables with the published Storm IDs.

Figures

The `Figure/` folder contains the final figures generated by the notebooks in `Codes/`. Re-running any notebook will regenerate the corresponding figure(s) from the `Data/` tables.

Usage

Requirements: Python 3.x, Jupyter, and standard scientific Python stack (e.g., `pandas`, `numpy`, `matplotlib`). Open any notebook in `Codes/` and run all cells to reproduce the corresponding figure under `Figure/`.